

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF MESOIONIC TRIAZOLES(I)

Compd. Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	λ_{max} (MeOH) $m\mu$ ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$)	Mol. Formula	% S	
					Calc.	Found
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ Ph	310–11	80	320 (3.60); 246 (26.41); 223 (21.44)	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	9.33	9.30
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OPh	274–75 dec	83	316 (5.12); 252 (23.80); 223 (24.21)	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	8.91	8.78
<i>p</i> -BrPh	308–09 dec	73	325 (3.24); 245.5(29.54); 214.5(25.32)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ S	7.84	7.65
<i>p</i> -I-Ph	293–94 dec	82	326 (5.31); 254 (31.09); 214.5(28.81)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ IN ₃ S	7.03	7.40
<i>p</i> -CNPh	335–36 dec	70	350 (3.99); 245.5(33.51); 217 (22.41)	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	9.01	8.78
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -Ph	300–01 dec	53	375 (3.54); 252 (28.30); 215.5(22.99)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	8.56	8.23
<i>m</i> -ClPh	290	55	325 (3.08); 242 (24.67); 220 (25.77)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ S	8.80	8.90
<i>m</i> -EtOPh	252–53	81	~300 (3.69)br; ~244 Sh 228 (26.20)	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	8.57	8.40
Ph and N-1 Ph = <i>p</i> -BrPh	318–19 dec	55	320 (2.86); 230–250 (broad band)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ S	7.84	7.60

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Mass Spectrometric Identification of Hydrazones of an Aromatic Aldehyde*

S. K. BHASIN & D. N. SEN

National Chemical Laboratory, Poona 8

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THE mass spectral fragmentation of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones,^{1,2} sulphonyhydrazones,³ N,N-dimethylhydrazones⁴ and some phenylhydrazones⁵ of aromatic aldehydes and ketones have been reported in literature. We became interested in the behaviour under electron impact of salicylaldehyde hydrazone and salicylaldehyde salicyloyl hydrazide—the two ligands used by us⁶ in the course of our

studies on metal chelates. The various ion peaks recorded in the mass spectra of these are given in tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—RELATIVE INTENSITIES OF FRAGMENTS FROM SALICYLALDEHYDE HYDRAZONE

m/e	Intensity %	m/e	Intensity %
136*	100.0	91	25.8
120	23.3	80	7.4
119	28.3	77	12.5
107	16.6	65	8.3

* molecular ion.

TABLE 2—RELATIVE INTENSITIES OF FRAGMENTS FROM SALICYLALDEHYDE SALICYLOYL HYDRAZIDE

m/e	Intensity %	m/e	Intensity %
256*	23.6	107	2.1
137	2.2	93	11.4
136	14.5	92	5.1
135	29.7	80	1.9
121	100.0	77	7.0
120	32.0	65	24.4
119	6.6	—	—

* molecular ion.

It was observed by Das *et al.*⁵ that straight cleavage of N-N bond is the most characteristic fragmentation mode of phenylhydrazones. This feature was also

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noted in the case of compounds reported here. The peaks at m/e 120 and m/e 119 observed in the mass spectrum of salicylaldehyde hydrazone can be considered to be due to γ -cleavage of the N-N bond resulting in the loss of the ammonia radical as follows :

The peaks at m/e 107 and m/e 91 suggest also a fragmentation,

Another possibility to obtain the peak at m/e 107 is due to fragmentation,

The peaks at m/e 80 and m/e 65 in the lower mass region are attributed to the skeletons

In the case of salicylaldehyde salicyloyl hydrazone, the γ -cleavage of N-N bond is evidenced by the peaks at m/e 136 and m/e 120, the two even electron ions subsequently undergoing hydrogen losses as shown :

The meta-stable peak at 73.5 (calcd. 73.0) supports this fragmentation mode. The peaks at m/e 137 and m/e 119 indicate a fragmentation due to rearrangement involving the migration of hydrogen atoms from carbon and nitrogen as shown :

This mode of fragmentation has been reported⁵ to be characteristic of benzaldehyde phenylhydrazone and its analogs. The peaks at m/e 135 and m/e 121 can be explained by the following chart :

A β -cleavage of the molecular ion appears to be responsible for the peak at m/e 107.

The intense peak at m/e 93 is attributed to the

fragment which loses a hydrogen atom

yielding .

The mass spectra of the compounds were recorded on CEC 21-110B double focussing mass spectrometer with an ionizing energy of 70 ev, both direct inlet and heated inlet systems having been used for sample vaporization.

Although literature methods^{7,8} were followed for the preparation of the compounds, the procedure for salicylaldehyde hydrazone was modified as follows : Salicylaldehyde (122 g; 1.0 mole) dissolved in 2440 g alcohol was added with stirring to an ice-cooled solution of 62.5 ml (1.0 mole) of 80% hydrazine hydrate (diluted to 100 ml) to obtain a white crystalline compound purified further by recrystallization from absolute alcohol. The purity of the compounds was checked by analysis and melting points.

References

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